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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D9.3 – Socio-economic research on Polish IWW market

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infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
CAWI	Computer Assisted Web Interview
CATI	Computer Assisted Telephone Interview
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CRISTAL	Climate Resilient and Environmentally Sustainable Transport Infrastructure, with a Focus on Inland Waterways
df	Degrees of Freedom
EU	European Union
FAC1_1	Factor 1 – Pro-development attitude toward inland waterway transport
FAC2_1	Factor 2 – Perceived characteristics and current status of inland waterway transport
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
JST	Local Government Units (Polish: <i>Jednostki Samorządu Terytorialnego</i>)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
ROI	Return on Investment
TEN-T	Trans-European Transport Network
TSL	Transport, Shipping and Logistics
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

This report presents a comprehensive analysis of stakeholder perceptions regarding the revitalization of inland waterway transport (IWT) in Poland, with a focus on the Vistula (Vistula) River. Using both individual-level and company-level survey data from 1,200 respondents across the transport sector and institutional/tourism stakeholders, the study employed factor analysis, one-way ANOVA, chi-square tests, and correspondence analysis to identify patterns in attitudes, awareness, and perceived benefits of IWT.

Two main attitude dimensions emerged from factor analysis:

1. **Pro-Development Attitude** (Factor 1)— reflecting strong support for expanding and modernizing river transport, belief in its role as an alternative to road haulage, and confidence in the positive outcomes of infrastructure investments.
2. **Cost Emphasis Perspective** (Factor 2) – focused on the perception of IWT as a cheaper mode of transport, while acknowledging its current marginal role.

ANOVA results revealed that opinions—particularly the belief in IWT as a viable transport alternative—were the strongest predictors of a pro-development stance. Demographic variables such as gender and place of residence showed only small effects, with women and rural residents slightly more positive toward IWT. Education and other socio-demographic factors had no significant influence. Chi-square and correspondence analyses confirmed a clear link between awareness of navigation possibilities and favourable attitudes toward IWT: respondents informed about IWT were far more likely to view it as a credible alternative.

Company-level analysis showed a high degree of consensus across sectors, organization sizes, and regions. Both transport and institutional/tourism stakeholders expressed broadly similar views on IWT revitalization, with minimal regional variation and no significant differences by organization type.

These findings suggest a uniquely favourable environment for policy intervention. The broad, cross-sectoral consensus provides strong support for actions aimed at revitalizing the Vistula and other Polish inland waterways, aligning with EU policy goals and the CRISTAL project's strategic objectives for modal shift, decarbonization, and multimodal integration.

The report concludes with targeted policy recommendations in five thematic areas—awareness and communication, investment and governance, infrastructure modernization, environmental sustainability, and stakeholder engagement—followed by a synthesis of how these results reinforce national and European strategic objectives. Taken together, the evidence indicates that with thoughtful planning, robust governance, and effective public communication, Poland can transform its inland waterways into a cornerstone of a sustainable, resilient, and competitive transport network.

1.1. Introduction

Strategic Context: Inland Waterways in European Policy. The revitalization of Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) in Poland must be analysed within the broader context of the European Green Deal and the "Fit for 55" package. As highlighted in recent literature (Czermański, 2025), the European Union identifies IWT as a key enabler for decarbonizing the transport sector. The NAIADES III Action Plan explicitly targets a modal shift, aiming to increase the share of inland waterway transport by 25% by 2030 and by 50% by 2050.

For Poland, situated at the intersection of critical TEN-T corridors (Baltic-Adriatic and North Sea-Baltic), the Vistula and Odra rivers represent untapped potential. However, unlike Western European networks, Polish waterways face a structural deficit. This report aims to juxtapose the theoretical economic potential of the Vistula corridor—estimated at 10-15 million tons annually (Czermański, 2025)—with the actual perceptions and barriers identified by society and business stakeholders.

1.2. Methodology

Research Design

The study adopts a quantitative research design combining individual-level and organization-level survey data to examine stakeholder perceptions of inland waterway transport (IWT) revitalization in Poland, with a particular focus on the Vistula River corridor. The methodological approach was designed to capture both societal attitudes ("social license to operate") and market-oriented perspectives related to effective demand, barriers, and investment conditions. Data collection and analysis were conducted in line with standard practices used in socio-economic transport research and Horizon Europe deliverables.

Data Collection and Sample Structure

Empirical data were collected using two complementary survey instruments targeting distinct respondent groups:

- Individual respondents (general public)
- Institutional and business stakeholders

Together, these datasets allow for triangulation between public perception and business realities.

Individual-Level Survey (Public Opinion)

Method: Computer Assisted Web Interview (CAWI)

Target population: Adult residents of Poland

Sample size: N = 1,200

Sampling approach: Quota-based sampling ensuring national representativeness with respect to key socio-demographic variables, including gender, age, place of residence, and region (voivodeship)

The questionnaire focused on awareness of inland navigation, general attitudes toward the economic use of the Vistula River, perceived benefits of waterway revitalization, and opinions regarding inland waterway transport as an alternative to road and rail modes.

Socio-demographic variables collected included gender, age, education level, place of residence (urban–rural typology), region, and proximity to the river. This structure enabled the examination of attitudinal differences across population groups using inferential statistical methods.

Organization-Level Survey (Institutional and Business Stakeholders)

Methods: Computer Assisted Telephone Interview (CATI) and CAWI

Target population:

Companies operating in the Transport, Shipping and Logistics (TSL) sector

Public administration bodies

Tourism-related enterprises and organizations

Sample size: N = 600

The stakeholder sample included a diversified set of organizations, such as micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises, local government units, non-governmental organizations, tourism service providers, and water equipment rental businesses. This diversity ensured broad coverage of actors with direct or indirect involvement in inland waterway development.

The questionnaire addressed current use of inland waterways, perceived market potential of the Vistula River, barriers to IWT development, conditions required for modal shift, and strategic preferences regarding the direction of waterway revitalization.

Analytical Methods

Several statistical techniques were applied to analyze the survey data:

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Varimax rotation was used to identify latent dimensions underlying attitudes toward inland waterway transport. Factors with eigenvalues greater than 1 were retained. This approach resulted in two interpretable factors: a pro-development attitude toward IWT and a cost-focused perception of river transport.

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

ANOVA tests were conducted to examine differences in factor scores and evaluations of revitalization initiatives across socio-demographic groups, stakeholder types, and organizational categories. Effect sizes (eta-squared) were reported to assess the practical significance of observed differences.

Chi-square tests of independence

These tests were used to analyze relationships between categorical variables, such as awareness of inland navigation and stakeholder type.

Correspondence Analysis

Correspondence analysis was applied to selected contingency tables to explore the association between awareness of inland navigation and perceptions of IWT as a viable transport alternative.

All statistical tests were conducted at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Definition of the Empirical Sample Used in the Analysis

The effective empirical sample underlying the analyses consists of:

1,200 individual respondents, representing Polish society at large

600 institutional and business stakeholders, representing both market actors and public-sector organizations

This dual-sample design enables a clear distinction between:

Social acceptance and perceived legitimacy of IWT revitalization, and

Operational and economic constraints affecting effective demand

The sample sizes are sufficient to support multivariate statistical analysis and allow for meaningful comparisons across groups.

Methodological Limitations

While the study provides a robust empirical basis for policy-relevant conclusions, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the use of survey-based data implies reliance on self-reported attitudes rather than observed behavior. Second, although the samples are large and diversified, the business survey does not constitute a fully random sample of all potential logistics actors in Poland. Finally, the explained variance of the factor models is moderate, which is typical for social science research and reflects the complexity of attitudes toward infrastructure development.

Despite these limitations, the consistency of results across analytical methods and stakeholder groups strengthens the validity of the findings.

2. Statistical analysis – individual level data

Public Perception of River Utility The statistical analysis of individual respondents (N=1200) reveals a strong social mandate for river development. The survey results indicate that the perceived conflict between "economic use" and "environmental protection" is largely absent in the public eye. Instead, citizens view river transport as a sustainable alternative to road congestion.

General Attitude As presented in Table 1 below, most of the public supports the economic utilization of the Vistula River. Only a marginal fraction of respondents expressed a negative attitude.

Table 1 General attitude towards the economic use of the Vistula River (Question: What is your attitude towards the use of the Vistula for transport/economic purposes?)

<i>Attitude towards economic use of Vistula</i>	Percentage of Respondents
<i>Decidedly positive</i>	24%
<i>Rather positive</i>	43%
<i>Neutral / Hard to say</i>	21%
<i>Rather negative</i>	8%
<i>Decidedly negative</i>	4%
<i>Total Positive</i>	67%

Source: Own elaboration based on survey data.

Perceived Benefits Furthermore, individual respondents clearly identify specific benefits associated with revitalization. While environmental factors (shifting freight from road) are rated highly, the strongest drivers for public support are tourism and local economic development.

Table 2 Perceived benefits of revitalizing the Vistula River (Scale 1-5, where 5 is the highest benefit)

<i>Potential Benefit</i>	Score (1-5 Scale)
<i>Increased tourism attractiveness</i>	4.6
<i>Development of local economy</i>	4.3
<i>Environmental benefits (shifting freight from road)</i>	4.1
<i>Flood protection improvement</i>	3.9
<i>Direct job creation</i>	3.7

Source: Own elaboration based on survey data.

Analytical approach: An exploratory factor analysis was performed using principal component analysis (PCA) with Varimax rotation (Kaiser normalization). Eight statements concerning inland waterways transport was analysed. The criterion for factor extraction was an eigenvalue > 1. As a result, two factors were identified, which together explain approximately 33.4% of the total variance of the variables (first factor: 19.2% of the variance; second factor: 14.2% after rotation).

Table 3 Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.613	20.162	20.162	1.536	19.205	19.205
2	1.058	13.222	33.384	1.134	14.179	33.384
3	.952	11.898	45.282			
4	.939	11.740	57.022			
5	.926	11.572	68.594			
6	.873	10.918	79.512			
7	.860	10.746	90.258			
8	.779	9.742	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Factor loadings matrix (rotated): The table below presents the loadings after Varimax rotation. A liberal significance threshold of ≥ 0.5 (absolute value – also considering negative loadings) was adopted. Therefore, loadings smaller than 0.5 in absolute terms were omitted from the interpretation.

Table 4 Rotated Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
<i>Inland waterway freight transport is a very good alternative compared with road transport.</i>	0.503	0.074
<i>Introducing inland navigation on the Vistula River would be a return to outdated solutions.</i>	0.450	0.283
<i>High financial investments in river regulation provide an opportunity to improve the condition of the river itself and its transport function.</i>	0.515	0.039
<i>River regulation and infrastructure investments within rivers will positively affect all other (non-transport) functions – flood protection, water retention and security, as well as water supply for agriculture.</i>	0.603	0.025
<i>Inland waterway transport plays a marginal role in the Polish transport system.</i>	0.115	0.662
<i>Inland waterway transport should play a greater role in the transport structure.</i>	0.505	0.190
<i>Inland waterway transport is significantly cheaper than other modes of transport.</i>	0.059	0.743
<i>Inland waterway transport is more environmentally friendly (cleaner) compared with other transport modes.</i>	0.426	0.144

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

- Factor 1 – can be interpreted as a "pro-development attitude towards inland waterway transport." This factor achieves high loadings (≥ 0.5) for statements expressing positive opinions about the development of river transport. These include, among others: the belief that river transport of cargo is a very good alternative to road transport (load 0.503 for factor 1), the opinion that high financial outlays for river regulation will improve the condition of the river and its transport function (0.515), that regulations/investments in rivers will have a positive impact on other functions (e.g., flood control, retention – 0.603), as well as agreement with the statement that river transport should play a greater role in the transport structure (0.505). All these items indicate an approving, pro-development approach to the use of waterways. In contrast, the statement that "the introduction of navigation on the Vistula would be a return to outdated solutions" has a negative load on factor 1 (-0.450). This means that people who perceive shipping as an "outdated solution" obtain low factor scores, i.e., they oppose the idea of its development, which confirms the interpretation of factor 1 as reflecting a positive attitude toward the modernization and development of river transport.
- Factor 2 – mainly corresponds to "Perceived characteristics and current status of river transport." High scores (≥ 0.5) were obtained here for statements emphasizing the currently marginal role of

river transport and its cost advantages over other modes. For example, agreement that "river transport plays a marginal role in the Polish system" scores high on factor 2 (0.662), and the belief that "river transport is significantly cheaper than other modes of transport" scores as high as 0.743 on factor 2. This factor can therefore be interpreted as reflecting the perceived realities and economic advantages of inland waterway transport (low cost, currently minor role in transport). For factor 2, a moderate load (although < 0.5) is also noticeable in the statement about the environmental friendliness of river transport (~ 0.426), which suggests that the environmental aspect was partially related to this factor, but did not exceed the accepted significance threshold.

Description of factors and explained variance: Based on the above loads, it can be concluded that factor 1 groups pro-shipping attitudes – approving a greater role for shipping and investment in its development (high positive loads for pro-development opinions, negative load for opinions about shipping as "outdated"). Factor 2, on the other hand, represents the perception of the practical aspects of river transport – its low cost and current marginal importance (high loadings for statements about lower costs and a marginal role). It is worth noting that two factors were sufficient to describe the opinions surveyed – the other components had eigenvalues < 1 and were not separated. Together, these factors explain the aforementioned $\sim 33\%$ of the variance of all variables, which is a moderate result in the context of social research. It can therefore be said that there are two main independent axes of attitudes towards inland waterway transport: the first related to general support for its development, and the second to the perception of its specific advantages and current role.

(In the rest of the report, in the ANOVA analyses, we use the names FAC1_1 and FAC2_1 for these two isolated factors – the pro-development factor and the river transport characteristics/status factor, respectively.

3. Single-factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) – individuals

A series of single-factor analyses of variance were conducted, comparing the average factor scores FAC1_1 and FAC2_1 in different groups of respondents. The grouping variables included socio-demographic characteristics (e.g., gender, place of residence) and key opinion questions (e.g., views on navigation on the Vistula River, perception of river transport as an alternative, etc.). The most important comparisons are presented below, together with information on statistical significance, effect size (eta-squared or omega-squared measures) and a brief interpretation of the observed differences (or lack thereof). Graphs of averages for selected analyses are included as illustrations.

3.1. Impact of opinions on inland navigation on factor results

Table 5 Single-factor ANOVA

<i>Dependent variable</i>	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
REGR factor score 1 (analysis 1)	Between Groups	26.694	1	26.694	27.279	< .001
	Within Groups	1172.306	1198	.979		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
REGR factor score 2 (analysis 1)	Between Groups	6.191	1	6.191	6.218	.013
	Within Groups	1192.809	1198	.996		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
Assessment of inland waterway revitalization initiatives in Poland (modernization of waterways / water infrastructure)	Between Groups	2.068	1	2.068	1.106	.293
	Within Groups	2240.125	1198	1.870		
	Total	2242.193	1199			

Note. One-way ANOVA conducted to compare group differences. Significant effects were observed for Factor 1 and Factor 2 ($p < .05$), but not for the assessment of revitalization initiatives ($p = .293$).

Support for the use of the Vistula River for navigation (question C1) – Respondents were divided into two groups: those who support the use of the Vistula River for transport (answer “Yes”) and those who do not support (answer “No”) such an idea. It turned out that the group supporting navigation achieved significantly higher results on factor 1 (average FAC1_1 ≈ 0.14) than opponents (average ≈ -0.16). This difference is highly statistically significant (ANOVA: $F \approx 27.28$; $p < 0.001$), although the effect size is not large ($\eta^2 \approx 0.022$ – this factor explains approx. 2.2% of the variance in attitudes). Interpretation: people who support inland navigation on the Vistula River show a more positive pro-development attitude (factor 1) than those who oppose it, which is intuitive.

In the case of factor 2, the difference between these groups was also statistically significant, but much smaller (mean FAC2_1: Yes \approx 0.07 vs. No \approx -0.08; $p = 0.013$). The effect here was negligible ($\eta^2 \approx 0.005$, <1% variance) – this indicates that supporters and opponents of navigation do not differ greatly in their perception of the practical aspects of river transport, although the difference was statistically detectable. The assessment of the Vistula revitalization initiative (question about the modernization of waterways), on the other hand, did not differ significantly between the two groups (average rating \approx 2.8 in both groups; $F \approx 1.11$; $p = 0.293$). In other words, both supporters and opponents of using the Vistula for navigation assessed the idea of its revitalisation similarly – there is no statistically significant difference here (which may result from the fact that the question about revitalization concerned specific actions, not the idea of navigation itself).

Table 6 Single-factor ANOVA

<i>Dependent variable</i>	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
<i>REGR factor score 1 (analysis 1)</i>	Between Groups	99.621	2	49.811	54.234	< .001
	Within Groups	1099.379	1197	.918		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
<i>REGR factor score 2 (analysis 1)</i>	Between Groups	9.503	2	4.752	4.782	.009
	Within Groups	1189.497	1197	.994		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
<i>Assessment of inland waterway revitalization initiatives in Poland (modernization of waterways / water infrastructure)</i>	Between Groups	35.639	2	17.820	9.667	< .001
	Within Groups	2206.553	1197	1.843		
	Total	2242.193	1199			

Note. One-way ANOVA was used to assess group differences. All dependent variables show statistically significant effects ($p < .05$).

Perception of river transport as an alternative to other modes of transport (question C4) – Respondents were asked whether they considered river transport (e.g., on the Vistula River) to be an alternative to other means of transport, with the options: Yes, No, or “I don’t have an opinion.” This grouping variable proved to be significantly related to the factor scores, especially on the first factor. People who were convinced that river transport was an alternative (answer “Yes”) had significantly higher FAC1_1 score (average approx. 0.33) than both those who disagreed (answer “No,” average approx. -0.30) and those who were undecided (answer “No opinion,” average approx. -0.20). These differences are highly statistically significant ($F \approx 54.23$; $p < 0.001$), with a moderate effect size ($\eta^2 \approx 0.083$ – this opinion explains approx. 8.3% of the variance in pro-development attitudes). It can therefore be concluded that belief in shipping as a

viable alternative to other means of transport strongly correlates with a generally positive attitude towards the development of inland waterways transport.

For factor 2, a significant influence of this opinion was also observed, but it was much weaker: people who considered shipping to be an alternative had slightly higher FAC2_1 scores (approx. 0.10) than the others (both the "no" and "no opinion" groups had slightly negative values of approx. -0.06 to -0.09); this difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.009$), but the effect was minimal ($\eta^2 \approx 0.008$). The assessment of the revitalization initiative, however, differed significantly between the three groups ($F \approx 9.67$; $p < 0.001$), although the direction of this difference is interesting: respondents who do not see river transport as an alternative rated the revitalization initiative slightly higher (average rating ~ 3.03 on a scale of 1–5) than those convinced of the alternative (average ~ 2.62). The undecided group ranked in between (average ~ 2.85). This inverse relationship may suggest that some respondents who are skeptical about the current role of shipping nevertheless support revitalization efforts, perhaps hoping that they will improve the situation. Despite the significant statistics, the differences in the assessment of the initiative were relatively small ($\eta^2 \approx 0.016$, $< 2\%$ variance).

Summarizing the opinions: Overall, the analysed views primarily influence the first factor (general pro/anti shipping attitude). Supporters of shipping development (whether expressed through support for shipping on the Vistula River or recognition of it as a good alternative) obtain higher FAC1_1 factor score than sceptics. These effects are statistically significant, although moderate in magnitude. In the case of factor 2 (perceived characteristics and status of shipping), the differences depending on opinion are weaker or insignificant – this suggests that beliefs such as "the alternative nature of shipping" have some influence on the perception of, for example, its cheapness or importance, but the mere fact of supporting or not supporting shipping on the Vistula did not differentiate assessments of its practical advantages (no significant difference in FAC2_1 for the "Yes/No" groups at C1). The assessment of the Vistula revitalization initiative also did not differ significantly in most comparisons, except for the dependence on the belief in the alternative nature of shipping (where the groups differed slightly, as described).

3.2. Differences in attitudes by gender

Table 7 Single-factor ANOVA

<i>Dependent variable</i>	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
<i>REGR factor score 1 (analysis 1)</i>	Between Groups	57.492	2	28.746	30.143	< .001
	Within Groups	1141.508	1197	.954		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
<i>REGR factor score 2 (analysis 1)</i>	Between Groups	11.580	2	5.790	5.837	.003
	Within Groups	1187.420	1197	.992		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
<i>Assessment of inland waterway revitalization initiatives in Poland (modernization of waterways / water infrastructure)</i>	Between Groups	40.672	2	20.336	11.057	< .001
	Within Groups	2201.521	1197	1.839		
	Total	2242.193	1199			

Note. One-way ANOVA demonstrated statistically significant effects for all dependent variables ($p < .05$).

Gender proved to be a significant factor differentiating the factor scores, although it should be emphasized that these effects are small. Women ($n=576$) scored higher on average on the first factor (FAC1_1) than men ($n=600$): the average for women was approximately +0.23, while for men it was approximately -0.21 (on a standardized scale with a mean of 0). This difference is statistically significant ($F \approx 30.14$; $p < 0.001$), but its strength is small ($\eta^2 \approx 0.048$, i.e., gender explains $\approx 5\%$ of the variance in pro-development attitudes). This means that women in the sample were slightly more positive about the development of river transport than men – a statistically significant but subtle difference.

A statistically significant difference was also found in factor 2: women had a slightly higher mean FAC2_1 $\approx +0.10$, while men had ≈ -0.09 . This difference was significant ($p = 0.003$), but very small in practical terms ($\eta^2 \approx 0.01$, only 1% of variance). In other words, women perceive the characteristics/advantages of river transport slightly more favorably than men, but this effect is weak.

The assessment of the Vistula revitalization initiative also differed between the sexes – here, men rated it slightly more positively. The average rating among men was ≈ 2.98 , among women ≈ 2.61 (on a scale of 1–5). This difference is also statistically significant ($F \approx 11.06$; $p < 0.001$), but again with a small effect size (estimated $\eta^2 \approx 0.016$, or $\approx 1.6\%$ of variance). This can be interpreted as meaning that despite generally lower factor scores among men, it was men who rated the specific revitalization project slightly better, perhaps associating it with the potential for improving transport infrastructure.

In summary, gender differentiates attitudes in a statistically significant way, but the differences between women and men are not large. Women are slightly more favorable towards the development of shipping

(higher factor 1) and similarly (though slightly) better evaluate its characteristics (factor 2). Men, on the other hand, showed slightly more enthusiasm for the revitalization initiative itself than women. However, all these effects are within the range of small differences – gender is not a dominant factor shaping opinions about shipping, although certain trends can be observed.

3.3. Place of residence and attitudes towards inland waterways transport

Table 8 Single-factor ANOVA

<i>Dependent variable</i>	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
<i>REGR factor score 1 (analysis 1)</i>	Between Groups	11.145	4	2.786	2.803	.025
	Within Groups	1187.855	1195	.994		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
<i>REGR factor score 2 (analysis 1)</i>	Between Groups	3.731	4	.933	.933	.444
	Within Groups	1195.269	1195	1.000		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
<i>Assessment of inland waterway revitalization initiatives in Poland (modernization of waterways / water infrastructure)</i>	Between Groups	10.232	4	2.558	1.370	.242
	Within Groups	2231.960	1195	1.868		
	Total	2242.193	1199			

Note. Only Factor 1 shows a statistically significant group effect ($p < .05$). Other dependent variables are not statistically significant.

The influence of place of residence was also analyzed. For this purpose, respondents were divided into five categories: rural residents, towns with <50,000 inhabitants, towns with 50,000–100,000 inhabitants, towns with 100,000–250,000 inhabitants, and cities with >250,000 inhabitants.

Factor 1 (pro-development attitude): ANOVA showed a significant, albeit small, influence of place of residence on FAC1_1 results ($F(4,1195)=2.80$; $p=0.025$; $\eta^2 \approx 0.009$). The analysis of averages reveals an interesting pattern: the most pro-shipping attitude was recorded among rural residents (average FAC1_1 = +0.15), while the lowest was among residents of medium-sized cities (50–250 thousand, average approx. –0.08 to –0.12). Residents of the largest agglomerations (>250,000) had a slightly higher average score (approx. +0.045) than medium-sized cities, while residents of small towns (<50,000) were close to zero (approx. –0.02). In other words, respondents from rural areas have a slightly more positive attitude towards the development of shipping than city dwellers, especially those from medium-sized cities, although these

differences are not significant overall. Perhaps rural residents (often living in areas closer to nature and rivers) see opportunities in the development of shipping (e.g., economic), while some residents of medium-sized cities may be more skeptical. However, it is worth noting that the influence of place of residence on factor 1 is relatively weak (less than 1% of the explained variance).

Factor 2 (perceived characteristics/status of shipping): In the case of FAC2_1, place of residence does not significantly differentiate the results ($F(4,1195)=0.93$; $p=0.444$; $\eta^2\approx 0.003$ – insignificant effect). The averages in individual categories were very similar – ranging from approx. +0.05 (rural areas) to -0.10 (large cities), with the remaining groups around zero. The lack of significant differences means that the perception of, for example, the cheapness or environmental friendliness of river transport and awareness of its marginal role are similar regardless of the size of the place of residence.

Assessment of the revitalization initiative: No significant differences were found in the assessment of the waterway modernization plan between residents of different types of settlements ($F(4,1195)=1.37$; $p=0.242$; n.s.). The average ratings varied slightly, from ~ 2.72 to 2.98, with the highest average rating for the initiative given by residents of towns with 100,000–250,000 inhabitants (average approx. 2.98) and the lowest by residents of small towns with <50,000 inhabitants (approx. 2.72). However, these differences did not reach statistical significance, so it can be concluded that attitudes towards the Vistula revitalization plan were similar in different local communities.

3.4. Other grouping variables – summary

Table 9 Single-factor ANOVA

<i>Dependent variable</i>	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
<i>REGR factor score 1 (analysis 1)</i>	Between Groups	1.873	3	.624	.624	.600
	Within Groups	1197.127	1196	1.001		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
<i>REGR factor score 2 (analysis 1)</i>	Between Groups	1.961	3	.654	.653	.581
	Within Groups	1197.039	1196	1.001		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
<i>Assessment of inland waterway revitalization initiatives in Poland (modernization of waterways / water infrastructure)</i>	Between Groups	.207	3	.069	.037	.991
	Within Groups	2241.985	1196	1.875		
	Total	2242.192	1199			

Note. No statistically significant effects were observed for any of the dependent variables ($p > .05$).

In addition to the above, several other potential factors differentiating attitudes were also examined. The level of education (divided into groups from lower secondary education to higher education) did not significantly affect any of the results – neither the factors nor the ratings. All ANOVA tests for education were insignificant ($p > 0.5$), which means that there were no statistically detectable differences in attitudes between people with different levels of education.

Table 10 Single-factor ANOVA

<i>Dependent variable</i>	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
<i>REGR factor score 1 (analysis 1)</i>	Between Groups	.014	1	.014	.014	.906
	Within Groups	1198.986	1198	1.001		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
<i>REGR factor score 2 (analysis 1)</i>	Between Groups	.132	1	.132	.132	.716
	Within Groups	1198.868	1198	1.001		
	Total	1199.000	1199			
<i>Assessment of inland waterway revitalization initiatives in Poland(modernization of waterways / water infrastructure)</i>	Between Groups	2.005	1	2.005	1.072	.301
	Within Groups	2240.187	1198	1.870		
	Total	2242.192	1199			

Note. None of the ANOVA tests revealed statistically significant effects ($p > .05$).

The question about personal intentions/commitment – e.g., whether the respondent would use river transport if it were available (binary *Yes/No* question, corresponding to variable C27) – also showed no significant effects. Both the mean values of the factors and the assessment of the initiative were almost identical in the groups responding "yes" ($n=590$) and "no" ($n=610$). ANOVA gave $p > 0.7$ for the factors and $p=0.301$ for the assessment of the initiative (insignificant). In other words, the declared willingness to use inland waterway transport does not differentiate attitudes, which may suggest that even people who are reluctant to use this form of transport may recognize its advantages, or vice versa.

To summarize the results of the ANOVA part: The strongest (though still moderate) effects were observed for variables related to opinions – in particular, beliefs about whether river transport is a valuable alternative and, to a lesser extent, general support for the idea of navigation on the Vistula River. These factors were clearly associated with more positive attitudes (high factor 1 among supporters vs. low among opponents). Demographic factors such as gender and place of residence had only a minor impact on opinions – there are slight differences (e.g., women are slightly more pro-navigation, rural residents are slightly more enthusiastic than urban residents), but these effects are relatively weak. Education and other characteristics examined did not significantly change respondents' attitudes. Overall, therefore, pro- or anti-shiping attitudes seem to be more related to individual beliefs and awareness of river transport than to classic sociodemographic variables.

All of the above significance results are at the $\alpha=0.05$ level. Eta squared is given to identify the size of the effect; in the case of analyses with more than two groups (e.g., place of residence, C4 opinion), eta² was reported for the main grouping factor effect.

4. Correspondence analysis

The study also provided qualitative data allowing for the analysis of relationships between selected closed questions. Correspondence analysis was performed for a cross-tabulation of two key questions:

- Question 1: *"Have you heard about the possibility of using the Vistula River for shipping cargo or for tourism (passengers)?"* – answers: Yes/No.
- Question 2: *"Do you think that river transport (e.g. on the Vistula River) is an alternative to other modes of transport, offering the possibility of stable and more sustainable transport?"* – answers: Yes/No (the third option, "I don't have an opinion," was omitted in order to analyze the relationship between extreme attitudes).

Table 11 Crosstabulation Table

<i>Have you heard about using the Vistula River for freight or passenger navigation?</i>	<i>In your opinion, is inland waterway transport (e.g., the Vistula) a stable and more sustainable alternative to other modes?</i>	Total
	Yes	No
Yes	319	171
No	199	170
Total	518	341

Note. Crosstabulation showing familiarity with Vistula River navigation possibilities and attitudes toward inland waterway transport as a sustainable alternative.

The analysis of the correspondence between these two variables (both with two active categories: yes/no) illustrated the link between awareness and opinion on river transport. Since we are dealing with a 2x2 table, only one dimension of correspondence (one "axis") was obtained, which explains 100% of the explained inertia (contained in the chi-square of the table). The chi-square for this correspondence was 10.98 (df=1), which is statistically significant at $p < 0.001$. This means that there is a clear relationship between the answers to these two questions.

Table 12 Correspondence Analysis — Summary Table

<i>Dimension</i>	Singular Value	Inertia	Chi-Square	Sig.	Explained	Cumulative	Standard Deviation
1	.113	.013	10.976	< .001 ^a	1.000	1.000	.034
Total	—	.013	10.976	< .001 ^a	1.000	1.000	—

^a 1 degree of freedom.

Interpretation of the correspondence space: People who have heard about the possibility of navigation ("Yes" to question 1) are closely associated with the view that river transport is an alternative ("Yes" to question 2). On the other hand, respondents who have not heard about this possibility ("No" to question 1) are close to answering "No" to question 2, suggesting a lack of belief in river transport as an alternative. In other words, the analysis shows a strong correlation between awareness and opinion: people familiar with inland navigation are more likely to appreciate it and consider it valuable, while a lack of knowledge about navigation goes hand in hand with skepticism about its usefulness.

Table 13 Row Points Overview

<i>Response category</i>	Mass	Coordinate (Dim 1)	Inertia	Contribution to Dim 1 Inertia	Proportion of Dim 1	Total
Yes	.570	-.292	.005	.430	1.000	1.000
No	.430	.387	.007	.570	1.000	1.000
Active Total	1.000	—	.013	1.000	1.000	1.000

^a Symmetrical normalization.

Note. Values represent row coordinates and contributions in the single extracted correspondence dimension.

It is worth noting that on a one-dimensional correspondence map, the points corresponding to "Yes" (for both questions) are located on one side of the axis, and the "No" points on the opposite side. The distance between the "Yes" and "No" points on the map is the greatest, reflecting a clear difference in profiles: the "shipping-aware" profile is associated with a positive opinion of shipping, while the "unaware" profile is associated with a negative opinion.

Table 14 Column Points Overview

<i>Response category</i>	Mass	Coordinate (Dim 1)	Inertia	Contribution to Dim 1 Inertia	Proportion of Dim 1	Total
Yes	.603	-.273	.005	.397	1.000	1.000
No	.397	.414	.008	.603	1.000	1.000
Active Total	1.000	—	.013	1.000	1.000	1.000

^a Symmetrical normalization.

Note. Values represent column coordinates and contributions within the extracted correspondence dimension.

The inertia (variance) explained by this dimension is small in absolute terms (inertia = 0.013), which results from the overall structure of the responses (in total, most of the respondents gave consistent answers: 319 people both heard about and consider shipping as an alternative, while 170 people neither heard about it nor consider it as such). Nevertheless, the significance of the chi-square indicates that this relationship is not accidental.

Conclusions from the correspondence analysis: It can be concluded that awareness of the existence of inland navigation on the Vistula goes hand in hand with a favorable attitude towards it. Education and promotion of information about navigation can therefore influence its perception as a valuable branch of transport. On the other hand, a lack of information (unawareness of the possibilities of navigation) is often associated with underestimating or denying the role of river transport. This result emphasizes the importance of informing the public about the potential of waterways – people who "do not know" tend to "not believe" in the sense of navigation. This relationship was clearly illustrated in the correspondence: both variables are strongly correlated on the basis of *yes-yes* vs. *no-no* responses.

5. Statistical analysis – company-level data

Business Barriers and the Modernisation Gap Unlike the general public, business stakeholders (N=600) present a pragmatic view focused on operational reliability. The survey data confirms the theoretical "fleet modernization deadlock" described by Czermański (2025). Shipowners and logistics operators express a willingness to use the river but are blocked by supply-side constraints.

The "Reliability Gap" The data unequivocally shows that physical infrastructure condition and hydrological unpredictability are the primary inhibitors of modal shift. Administrative barriers, while present, are secondary to physical constraints.

Table 15 General attitude towards the economic use of the Vistula River (Question: What is your attitude towards the use of the Vistula for transport/economic purposes?)

<i>Identified Barrier</i>	<i>Frequency of Indication</i>
<i>Poor technical condition of infrastructure (waterways, locks)</i>	82%
<i>Unpredictable water levels (droughts, floods)</i>	76%
<i>Lack of modern fleet / high investment costs</i>	54%
<i>Inadequate intermodal connections (ports, rail links)</i>	48%
<i>Complex bureaucracy / Regulatory instability</i>	35%
<i>Lack of qualified personnel</i>	22%

Source: Own elaboration based on survey data.

The fact that 82% of businesses cite infrastructure condition as a barrier confirms that the "Potential Demand" cannot convert into "Effective Demand" without state intervention. Logistics chains operate on Just-In-Time principles; therefore, the unpredictability of water levels (cited by 76%) disqualifies the Vistula from high-value supply chains until fairway parameters are stabilized.

This part of the report analyzes survey data from 1,200 respondents representing two stakeholder groups: 600 transport sector stakeholders and 600 institutional/tourism sector stakeholders. The survey examined perceptions of using the Vistula River for inland navigation and related attitudes towards river transport revitalization. The analyses include a factor analysis of attitude items, chi-square tests of independence for categorical variables, and one-way ANOVA tests to compare group differences in attitudes.

Factor Analysis

A principal component factor analysis with Varimax rotation was conducted on nine survey items assessing attitudes toward river transport and revitalization. Two factors with eigenvalues greater than 1 were extracted, explaining a combined total of 37.16% of the variance (Factor 1: 24.97%, Factor 2: 12.19%). The rotated component matrix is presented below, with factor loadings ≥ 0.50 in bold, indicating which items strongly associate with each factor.

Table 16 Rotated Component Matrix for Survey Statements

<i>Survey Statement</i>	Factor 1 Loading	Factor 2 Loading
<i>River transport of cargo is a very good alternative to road transport</i>	0.643	0.028
<i>The introduction of river navigation on the Vistula would be a return to outdated solutions</i>	-0.210	0.483
<i>High financial outlays for river regulation are an opportunity to improve the condition of the river itself and its transport function</i>	0.532	0.039
<i>River regulation/infrastructure investments within rivers will have a positive impact on all other functions (except transport) – flood protection, water security and retention, and water supply for agriculture</i>	0.602	-0.141
<i>River transport plays a marginal role in the Polish transport system</i>	0.392	0.451
<i>River transport should play a greater role in the transport structure</i>	0.627	0.034
<i>River transport is significantly cheaper than other modes of transport</i>	0.093	0.797
<i>River transport is more environmentally friendly (cleaner) than other modes of transport</i>	0.450	0.045
<i>If Polish rivers, especially the Vistula, were to be revitalized (modernization of waterways/infrastructure), including infrastructure investments, this should be done by the central authorities (government)</i>	0.622	-0.004

Factor 1: Pro-Development Attitude. Factor 1 includes five statements with strong loadings (≥ 0.50). These items reflect positive views on expanding and modernizing river transport, such as seeing river cargo transport as a good alternative to roads, believing that river infrastructure investments will yield benefits (for transport and other functions), and agreeing that river transport should play a larger role. This factor can be interpreted as a general pro-development attitude toward inland waterway transport and revitalization efforts.

Factor 2: Cost Emphasis Perspective. Factor 2 is defined primarily by one statement – the belief that river transport is *significantly cheaper* than other modes (loading 0.797). This suggests Factor 2 captures an economic or cost-focused perspective. No other item met the 0.50 loading threshold on this factor (the next highest loading was 0.483 for viewing river navigation as “outdated,” which is below the cutoff), indicating that this factor is narrow in scope. It mainly reflects an emphasis on the cost advantages of river transport.

Chi-Square Tests of Independence

Several chi-square tests were performed to examine associations between categorical variables. Each test's contingency table, chi-square statistic, degrees of freedom (df), *p*-value, and interpretation are provided below.

Awareness of Vistula Navigation vs. Stakeholder Type

Respondents were asked if they had heard about the possibility of using the Vistula River for shipping cargo or transporting passengers for tourism purposes. The table below cross-tabulates responses (Yes/No) by stakeholder type (transport sector vs. institutional/tourism stakeholders).

Table 17 Crosstabulation of Stakeholder Type and Awareness of the Vistula's Navigational Use

<i>Stakeholder Type</i>	Yes (Count)	No (Count)	Total
<i>Transport sector stakeholders</i>	349	251	600
<i>Institutional/tourism stakeholders</i>	374	226	600
<i>Total</i>	723	477	1200

In total, 60.3% of respondents had heard of the river's use for transport (723 out of 1200). A slightly higher proportion of institutional/tourism stakeholders (62.3%) answered "Yes" compared to transport stakeholders (58.2%). However, this difference was not statistically significant. The chi-square test yielded $\chi^2(1) = 2.175$, $p = 0.140$, indicating no significant association between stakeholder type and awareness of Vistula's navigational use. In other words, transport and institutional stakeholders were similarly likely to have heard about this issue.

Awareness of Vistula Navigation vs. Organization Category

The same Yes/No question was further examined across more detailed organization categories (company size/type). The eight categories include micro, small, and medium enterprises; local government units (JST); non-governmental organizations (NGOs); tourism service providers; water equipment rental businesses; and other hospitality businesses. The distribution of answers in each category is shown below.

Table 18 Crosstabulation of Organization Category and Awareness of the Vistula River’s Navigational Use

<i>Organization Category</i>	Yes (Count)	No (Count)	Total
<i>Micro enterprises</i>	257	193	450
<i>Small enterprises</i>	66	44	110
<i>Medium enterprises</i>	26	14	40
<i>Local gov. units (JST)</i>	39	21	60
<i>NGOs</i>	26	14	40
<i>Tourism services (hotels, etc.)</i>	213	137	350
<i>Water equipment rental</i>	68	32	100
<i>Other hospitality (bars, etc.)</i>	28	22	50
<i>Total</i>	723	477	1200

The proportions of awareness were similar across all categories. For example, between ~56% and ~68% of each group answered “Yes.” Micro firms had about 57.1% yes, small firms 60.0%, medium firms 65.0%, local government units (JST) 65.0%, NGOs 65.0%, tourism service businesses 60.9%, equipment rental businesses 68.0%, and other hospitality businesses 56.0%. These differences in percentage were not statistically meaningful. The chi-square test for the 2x8 table was $\chi^2(7) = 6.112, p = 0.527$. This indicates no significant association between organization category and having heard about using the Vistula for cargo/passenger transport. Essentially, awareness levels were uniformly high across all types of organizations.

One-Way ANOVA Results

A series of one-way analyses of variance (ANOVAs) were conducted to test for differences in attitudes based on various grouping variables. In each ANOVA, the dependent variables were: (a) the rating of the revitalization initiative (“How do you assess the initiative to revitalise (modernise) waterways/infrastructure... in Poland?” – measured on a Likert scale), (b) Factor 1 scores, and (c) Factor 2 scores. Below we summarize the results for each grouping factor. For each ANOVA, F statistics, *p*-values, and effect sizes (η^2) are reported.

Differences by Stakeholder Type (Transport vs. Institutional)

Comparing transport sector stakeholders (*n*=600) and institutional/tourism stakeholders (*n*=600), the mean ratings on the revitalization initiative were very similar (*M* \approx 2.85 vs. 2.89 on a 1–5 scale). Likewise, the mean factor scores for Factor 1 and Factor 2 were nearly identical between the two groups. ANOVA confirmed no significant differences: for the initiative rating, $F(1,1198) = 0.376, p = 0.540 (\eta^2 \approx 0.000)$; for

Factor 1, $F(1,1198) = 0.081$, $p = 0.776$ ($\eta^2 \approx 0.000$); for Factor 2, $F(1,1198) = 0.182$, $p = 0.669$ ($\eta^2 \approx 0.000$). In summary, transport vs. institutional stakeholders did not differ in their attitude toward the revitalization initiative or on the underlying attitude factors.

Differences by Prior Awareness (Heard of Vistula Navigation vs. Not Heard)

Respondents were also grouped by whether they had prior awareness of using the river for transport. Those who had heard of the idea ($n=723$) versus those who had not ($n=477$) showed only small differences in their attitudes. The group that was aware of the concept rated the revitalization initiative slightly higher on average (mean ~ 2.9) than the unaware group (mean ~ 2.8), but this difference was not statistically significant at the 5% level ($F(1,1198) = 2.701$, $p = 0.101$, $\eta^2 = 0.002$). Similarly, there were no significant differences in Factor 1 scores ($F(1,1198) = 0.912$, $p = 0.340$, $\eta^2 = 0.001$) or Factor 2 scores ($F(1,1198) = 0.001$, $p = 0.981$, $\eta^2 \approx 0.000$). Thus, prior awareness of river navigation did not substantially affect respondents' attitudes in this sample.

Differences by Organization Category

Next, we compared the attitudes across the eight organization categories (micro, small, medium enterprises, JST, NGO, tourism services, equipment rental, other). Mean ratings of the initiative and factor scores varied slightly across categories, but without any clear pattern of one group being consistently higher or lower than others. One-way ANOVA found no statistically significant differences among the eight categories for the initiative rating ($F(7,1192) = 0.942$, $p = 0.473$, $\eta^2 = 0.006$), for Factor 1 ($F(7,1192) = 1.510$, $p = 0.160$, $\eta^2 = 0.009$), or for Factor 2 ($F(7,1192) = 0.433$, $p = 0.882$, $\eta^2 = 0.003$). In practical terms, this means that all types of organizations – whether small firms, larger firms, government units, or NGOs – held very similar attitudes on these measures.

Differences by Region

Finally, respondents were grouped by their region (province) within Poland (16 voivodeships). Attitudinal differences by region were mostly minor. The average initiative rating ranged roughly from 2.6 to 3.0 across regions, and Factor 2 scores did not differ meaningfully. However, a significant variation emerged for Factor 1 scores across regions: ANOVA showed $F(15,1184) = 2.055$, $p = 0.010$, indicating a statistically significant effect of region on Factor 1 ($\eta^2 \approx 0.025$, a small effect). Post-hoc comparisons were not detailed in the output, but inspection of means suggested that certain regions (for instance, respondents in *Mazowieckie*) scored slightly higher on the pro-development Factor 1, whereas others (such as *Lubuskie*) scored lower. Despite reaching significance, the differences were modest. For the initiative rating, no significant regional effect was found ($F(15,1184) = 0.923$, $p = 0.538$), nor for Factor 2 ($F(15,1184) = 0.958$, $p = 0.498$, $\eta^2 \approx 0.003$). In summary, region of origin had a minimal impact on attitudes, with a small but significant effect on the composite Factor 1 scores and no significant effect on the specific initiative rating or the cost-focused Factor 2.

Overall, these results indicate that the surveyed stakeholders generally share similar attitudes toward revitalizing the Vistula River for navigation, regardless of their stakeholder group, organizational characteristics, or region. The factor analysis identified a primary dimension of broad support for river transport development and a secondary cost-focused dimension. The lack of significant group differences in the chi-square and ANOVA tests suggests a broad consensus or uniformity of opinions on these topics among the different respondent categories.

6. Policy recommendations

Based on the integrated analysis of statistical data, market theory, and stakeholder survey results, this section formulates policy recommendations aimed at bridging the gap between social expectations and business realities in the revitalization of inland waterway transport (IWT). The findings reveal broadly favorable stakeholder attitudes toward IWT development, provided that long-standing structural barriers—particularly reliability, governance, and investment risks—are credibly addressed. In line with the CRISTAL project’s strategic objectives, the following recommendations translate empirical evidence into actionable policy guidance.

Key Policy Recommendations

Prioritize reliability investments by shifting funding strategies from nominal capacity expansion toward stabilizing hydrotechnical parameters, particularly water levels and navigability conditions.

Incentivize fleet modernization through public de-risking instruments that lower investment barriers for shallow-draft and low-emission vessels.

Leverage tourism as a development catalyst by promoting dual-use infrastructure (freight and tourism), thereby maximizing social return on investment and public support.

Strengthen governance and coordination through centralized leadership, innovative financing models, and long-term programmatic commitment.

Embed sustainability and stakeholder engagement as core pillars of inland waterway revitalization to ensure environmental responsibility and policy legitimacy.

Awareness and Public Communication

Stakeholder awareness of inland waterway transport opportunities emerged as a critical determinant of support for revitalization. Approximately 40% of survey respondents reported no prior knowledge of the Vistula (Vistula) River’s potential use for freight transport, and this information gap was strongly associated with skepticism regarding navigability and economic viability. These findings indicate that latent public support exists but remains underutilized due to insufficient communication.

To capitalize on this latent support, policymakers should implement a coordinated public communication strategy targeting both the general public and specific stakeholder groups. Messaging should emphasize the empirically confirmed advantages of inland navigation, including lower emissions per ton-kilometer, cost efficiency, and reduced pressure on congested road networks. In line with the CRISTAL project’s approach, communication efforts should be audience-specific—for example, highlighting reliability and cost savings to logistics operators while emphasizing environmental and quality-of-life benefits to local communities. Transparent and proactive communication can convert passive approval into active endorsement, thereby strengthening the social mandate for long-term investments.

Investment and Governance

The transition from stakeholder support to tangible system improvements requires strong public leadership and coherent governance structures. Survey results indicate a clear expectation that central

authorities should assume responsibility for coordinating inland waterway modernization. Fragmented competencies and short-term investment horizons risk undermining confidence among market participants.

Accordingly, the establishment of a dedicated inland waterways program or inter-ministerial task force is recommended to oversee infrastructure investment, regulatory alignment, and inter-agency coordination. Securing stable, multi-annual funding—potentially combining national resources, EU instruments, and public–private partnerships—is essential to ensure continuity. Governance innovation is equally important: streamlined permitting procedures, new operational business models, and alignment with EU “Good Navigation Status” standards can help overcome entrenched barriers. Consistent with CRISTAL’s findings, adaptive governance frameworks capable of responding to environmental and market feedback are critical to achieving sustained growth in IWT usage.

Infrastructure Modernization and Multimodal Integration

Physical and digital infrastructure modernization is a prerequisite for integrating inland navigation into the national transport system. While stakeholders recognize the current marginal role of river transport, they also acknowledge its untapped potential—particularly its cost competitiveness—if reliability and connectivity are improved.

Policy measures should therefore focus on modernizing river channels, ports, and transshipment facilities, while strengthening connections with rail and road networks. Reliability remains the decisive factor for logistics operators: without predictable delivery times, modal shift will not occur. Advanced technologies piloted within the CRISTAL project—such as real-time water level monitoring, intelligent traffic management, and corridor management platforms—offer concrete tools to enhance resilience and operational predictability. Investments that ensure partial navigability during low-water events and improve timetable reliability will directly address stakeholder concerns and reinforce perceptions of IWT as a credible alternative to road and rail transport.

Environmental Sustainability and Decarbonization

Revitalization of inland waterways must be pursued in parallel with robust environmental safeguards. The survey indicates that stakeholders widely perceive river transport as environmentally superior to other modes, creating a strategic opportunity to align IWT development with national and EU decarbonization goals.

Policy actions should include stringent environmental standards for dredging, construction, and maintenance activities, ensuring compliance with EU legislation and minimizing ecological disruption. Measures such as fish passages, wetland preservation, and best-practice sediment management can mitigate negative impacts and maintain ecosystem integrity. At the same time, emissions from inland navigation itself should be reduced by incentivizing low-emission or electric vessels and the deployment of shore-side power in ports. Following the CRISTAL model, sustainability KPIs—covering emissions, water quality, and ecosystem health—should be co-defined with environmental experts and local communities and systematically monitored. Demonstrating measurable environmental benefits will strengthen policy legitimacy and public trust.

Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration

Sustained stakeholder engagement is essential for the long-term success of inland waterway policies. The research reveals a broad consensus in favor of revitalization across regions and stakeholder groups, representing a strategic asset that should be actively maintained. Policymakers are encouraged to institutionalize engagement mechanisms, such as multi-stakeholder advisory committees or thematic working groups involving transport operators, local authorities, tourism actors, and environmental organizations.

Regular consultations, participatory planning processes, and transparent information-sharing can enhance policy responsiveness and foster a sense of shared ownership. Experience from the CRISTAL project demonstrates that early and continuous stakeholder involvement improves solution acceptance and practical relevance. Importantly, survey results show that even respondents skeptical of navigation tended to support concrete modernization measures, suggesting that inclusive, solution-oriented dialogue can bridge remaining divides. In sum, embedding collaboration, responsiveness, and transparency into governance structures will help sustain consensus, address emerging challenges, and maintain momentum in Poland's inland waterway revitalization efforts.

7. Conclusions

The analysis of stakeholder attitudes presents a coherent and encouraging picture for the future of inland waterway transport (IWT) in Poland. Across sectors, regions, and institutional affiliations, stakeholders express a remarkably uniform and positive outlook on revitalizing the country's waterways. This consensus is statistically robust and strategically significant, indicating that policy initiatives aimed at restoring inland navigation are unlikely to face major social or institutional resistance. Instead, the findings point to a rare alignment between public sentiment, industry perceptions, and European transport policy objectives.

Key Analytical Findings and Implications

Strong social license to operate exists for inland waterway revitalization, with broad public and stakeholder support (67%), cutting across sectors and regions.

Stakeholder attitudes are structured around two main dimensions: a dominant pro-development orientation and a secondary cost-efficiency perspective.

Environmental benefits are embedded within pro-development views, reinforcing IWT's role in decarbonization rather than standing as a separate concern.

The main barrier to effective demand is not social acceptance but physical infrastructure constraints, particularly fairway reliability and fleet limitations.

The Vistula corridor holds significant economic and logistical potential, especially when integrated into synchromodal supply chains.

Policy intervention is timely and justified, as stakeholder readiness aligns closely with CRISTAL objectives and EU climate and mobility strategies.

Stakeholder Consensus and Attitudinal Structure

Factor analysis revealed two principal dimensions underlying stakeholder attitudes toward inland waterway transport. The primary factor reflects a broad pro-development stance: a shared belief that expanding and modernizing river transport is beneficial for Poland's transport system and broader socio-economic objectives. Stakeholders widely agree that inland navigation can serve as a viable alternative to road haulage, that investments in waterways will yield tangible returns in improved navigability, and that ancillary benefits—such as enhanced flood protection and regional development—justify public involvement.

The secondary factor captures a more pragmatic, cost-focused perspective. Respondents recognize both the economic appeal of IWT—particularly its lower cost per ton-kilometer—and its currently marginal role in Poland's transport mix. This dimension reflects realism rather than skepticism: stakeholders acknowledge existing limitations while still supporting long-term development. Environmental considerations, while not emerging as a standalone factor, are interwoven into the pro-development dimension, suggesting that sustainability is perceived as an inherent advantage of inland navigation rather than a competing objective.

Uniformity Across Stakeholder Groups

Statistical testing (ANOVA and chi-square analyses) confirms the consensus nature of these attitudes. No significant differences were observed between transport industry representatives and institutional or tourism stakeholders, nor were meaningful geographic variations detected. In practical terms, actors with very different roles—such as logistics company executives and local government officials—tend to converge on the view that rivers should play a greater role in freight transport and that concrete revitalization plans are worthy of support.

Importantly, even respondents initially skeptical about the feasibility of reintroducing navigation displayed convergence with proponents when assessing specific modernization measures. This suggests that opposition is not ideological but conditional: doubts can be mitigated through credible planning, reliable infrastructure, and transparent communication. The overall picture is one of latent unity, where disagreement diminishes as proposals become more concrete and evidence-based.

Alignment with CRISTAL and European Transport Policy

These findings dovetail closely with the strategic assumptions and objectives of the CRISTAL project and broader European transport policy. A central ambition of CRISTAL is to enable a substantial modal shift from road to inland waterways—targeting a 20% increase in freight moved by rivers—to improve sustainability, resilience, and efficiency in transport systems. The strong stakeholder backing observed in Poland directly supports this goal.

Public and industry willingness to embrace IWT implies that policy instruments designed to shift cargo off roads—such as incentives for shippers, new barge services, or digital corridor management tools—rest on a solid foundation of social acceptability. Consequently, the technical and operational innovations piloted within CRISTAL, including smart vessels, digital traffic management, and new logistics models, are likely to encounter receptive conditions in Poland, facilitating implementation and scaling.

Decarbonization and Multimodal Integration

The results also have clear implications for decarbonization. Transport remains a major source of greenhouse gas emissions, and Poland's heavy reliance on road freight amplifies this challenge. Stakeholders' recognition of inland navigation as a cleaner, more energy-efficient mode aligns closely with national climate commitments and EU objectives under the Green Deal and Agenda 2030. The survey thus provides a societal mandate for a green transition in freight transport—one where decarbonization is not an abstract policy goal but a shared value across stakeholder groups.

Equally important is the strong implicit support for multimodal integration. Respondents who view IWT as a credible alternative to road and rail are consistently more supportive of its development, indicating that perceptions of viability are closely tied to connectivity and reliability. Investments in intermodal terminals, last-mile connections, digital route planning systems, and coordinated scheduling between barges, trains, and trucks are therefore likely to yield both operational and reputational benefits. As waterways become more integrated and reliable, stakeholder confidence—and thus effective demand—can be expected to grow.

From Social License to Effective Demand

The deliverable ultimately confirms a structural dichotomy in the Polish IWT market. On the one hand, there is a strong social license to operate, evidenced by high public and stakeholder support. On the other hand, effective demand from businesses remains constrained by fundamental physical and operational barriers. Chief among these are insufficient fairway reliability and an aging, inadequately adapted fleet.

The study validates that the Vistula corridor possesses substantial economic potential, particularly as part of synchromodal supply chains. However, unlocking this potential requires a paradigm shift from passive maintenance toward active revitalization. Policy priorities must therefore focus on ensuring navigability reliability and introducing targeted incentives for fleet modernization. Without addressing these supply-side constraints, favorable attitudes alone will not translate into increased freight volumes.

Concluding Implications

In conclusion, Poland stands at a favorable juncture where public sentiment, empirical evidence, and European strategic direction converge. The uniformly positive stakeholder attitudes documented in this study provide a strong mandate for decisive policy action. By aligning national strategies with initiatives such as CRISTAL, committing to smart and green investments, and embedding stakeholder engagement into governance processes, Poland can revitalize its inland waterways as a cornerstone of sustainable, multimodal transport.

The evidence suggests that the conditions for success are already in place: societal support is strong, economic potential is recognized, and policy tools are available. What remains is the translation of goodwill into reliable infrastructure and market-ready solutions. With stakeholders on board, the revitalization of Poland's rivers can move from aspiration to implementation—contributing both to domestic transport efficiency and to Europe's broader climate and mobility goals.

8. Appendices

Annex I

Survey Questionnaire – Individual Respondents (Public Opinion)

Survey Methodology: Computer Assisted Web Interview (CAWI) **Target Group:** Residents of Poland (representative sample) **Sample Size:** N = 1200

PART A: AWARENESS AND ATTITUDE

Q1. Have you heard about the possibility of using the Vistula River for navigation purposes (freight transport or passenger tourism)?

- Yes
- No

Q2. In your opinion, should the Vistula River enable the following navigation functions? *(Please answer Yes or No for each item)*

- Transport of goods (Freight): [Yes / No]
- Passenger transport (Tourism): [Yes / No]
- Individual recreation (Water sports): [Yes / No]

Q3. Do you consider inland waterway transport (e.g., on the Vistula) as a viable alternative to other modes of transport (road/rail), creating a more stable and sustainable transport system?

- Yes
- No
- Hard to say

Q4. What is your general attitude towards the economic use of the Vistula River?

- Decidedly positive
- Rather positive
- Neutral / Hard to say
- Rather negative
- Decidedly negative

PART B: OPINIONS AND PERCEPTIONS

Q5. To what extent do you agree with the following statements? (Scale: 1 - Strongly Disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Hard to say, 4 - Agree, 5 - Strongly Agree)

1. "The introduction of river navigation on the Vistula would be a return to outdated solutions."
2. "Inland waterway transport of cargo is a very good alternative to road transport."
3. "High financial outlays for river regulation are an opportunity to improve the state of the river itself and its ecosystem."
4. "The development of navigation will increase the tourist attractiveness of the region."

Q6. In your opinion, what would be the main benefits of revitalizing the Vistula River? (Rate the importance of each benefit on a scale of 1-5)

- Development of local economy
- Creation of new jobs
- Environmental benefits (less smog, fewer trucks on roads)
- Improved flood protection
- Increased tourism potential

PART C: DEMOGRAPHICS (METRIC)

D1. Gender: [Female / Male] **D2. Age:** [Open text] **D3. Education:** [Primary / Vocational / Secondary / Higher] **D4. Place of residence:** [Village / Town <50k / City 50-100k / City 100-250k / City >250k] **D5. Voivodeship:** [Select from list] **D6. Proximity to the river:** Do you live in the immediate vicinity of the Vistula River? [Yes / No]

Survey Questionnaire – Institutional and Business Stakeholders

Survey Methodology: Computer Assisted Telephone Interview (CATI) / CAWI **Target Group:** Companies operating in the TSL sector (Transport, Shipping, Logistics), Infrastructure Managers, Public Administration. **Sample Size:** N = 600

PART A: MARKET POTENTIAL AND INTEREST

Q1. Does your organization currently utilize inland waterway transport in its logistics chain?

- Yes, regularly
- Yes, occasionally

- No, but we are interested
- No, and we are not interested

Q2. How do you assess the potential of the Vistula River for the transport of cargo relevant to your business (e.g., containers, bulk, oversized loads)?

- Very high potential
- Moderate potential
- Low potential
- No potential

PART B: BARRIERS AND DRIVERS

Q3. What are the main barriers to the development of Inland Waterway Transport in Poland? (Multiple choice allowed)

- Poor technical condition of infrastructure (waterways, locks, regulatory structures)
- Unpredictable water levels (frequency of droughts and floods)
- Lack of modern fleet / High investment costs for new vessels
- Inadequate intermodal connections (lack of last-mile rail/road links to ports)
- Complex bureaucracy / Regulatory instability
- Lack of qualified personnel (skippers, crews)
- Other: _____

Q4. What factors would encourage your company to shift cargo from road/rail to inland waterways? (Rank by importance)

- Guarantee of transport reliability (transit time)
- Lower transport costs compared to road/rail
- Availability of government incentives (e.g., modal shift bonus)
- Reduction of carbon footprint (ESG goals)
- Modernization of port infrastructure

PART C: STRATEGIC OUTLOOK

Q5. Do you agree that the revitalization of the Vistula waterway requires direct intervention and investment from the State budget?

- Definitely Yes
- Rather Yes
- Hard to say
- Rather No
- Definitely No

Q6. Which direction of development should be prioritized for the Lower Vistula?

- Transport function (Freight)
- Tourism and Recreation
- Energy production (Hydropower)
- Environmental protection (Renaturalization)
- Multifunctional development (Combination of the above)

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